

Glacial Lake Observatory

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Welcome to the inaugural newsletter of the **Glacial Lake Observatory (GLO)**.

These newsletters will share regular updates from the GLO project, including fieldwork highlights, research and data insights, outreach activities and more from our work to understand glacial lake dynamics across High Mountain Asia.

As glaciers disappear, glacial lakes are increasing in number and size. GLO combines satellite observations, field measurements, and modelling, to catalogue and monitor these lakes, quantify water storage, and improve understanding of associated flood hazards. Our aim is to provide open, science-based information that supports preparedness, risk reduction, and informed decision-making for mountain communities.

FIELDWORK – 2025 SUMMARY

From **May-June 2025**, the GLO team undertook fieldwork surveying glacial lakes and downstream valleys on a 200 km circular route in **Sagarmatha National Park**. They were joined by Research Associate Rajendra Shrestha ([NDRI](#)) and Prof. Jason Gulley on behalf of the New York Times.

Field methods

- ✓ Sonar surveys (packraft and RC boat)
- ✓ Drone surveys
- ✓ Global Navigation Satellite System surveys
- ✓ 360° photography

30
Lakes surveyed

200 km
Distance covered

12,000 m
Elevation gain

Data collected during the 2025 season is currently being processed, with the GLO team returning to the Himalayas in **Spring 2026...**

With thanks to Nepali guides Mahesh, Kaji, and HRE porters

Zoom in - can you spot the kayak?

Dig Tsho (2025)

DATA INSIGHTS

Over the past year, GLO has been cataloguing published glacial lake datasets covering glacier area, volume, depth, and other geophysical characteristics, while also developing a new glacial lake inventory focused initially on the Nepal–transboundary region.

This new dataset maps glacial lakes from 2017–2024 from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery using automated deep-learning methods and is currently available as a pre-print. Key statistics from the dataset are shown in the right-hand column.

To date, GLO has compiled 65,431 glacial lake outlines from 11 existing inventories across High Mountain Asia, together with 178 glacial lake volume records, representing more than 900,000 individual depth data points.

In the coming months, GLO will continue to expand this data catalogue, which will soon be openly accessible through the new GLO online data platform.

22,419
Lakes outlines mapped

4150
Individual lakes

169 km²
Mean annual lake area

5.78 km²
Largest lake

61%
of lakes are within the Koshi basin

Glacial lakes mapped in the new GLO dataset

[READ THE PRE-PRINT HERE](#)

OUTREACH

✓ Otley Science Festival

In November we welcomed 500+ visitors to explore the Himalayas in 360° using our VR headsets

✓ Spotlight Series Feature

GLO research was featured in the University of Leeds Spotlight Series, alongside other Leeds-based Himalayan research.

Read more [here](#).

✓ 'How to Fix...' podcast

Dr Lauren Rawlins was featured in the University of Leeds podcast series alongside Prof. Duncan Quincey and British Mountaineer Kenton Cool discussing Himalayan glacier research. Listen [here](#).

✓ New York Times Article

GLO fieldwork was featured in the NYT by Prof. Jason Gulley, who joined the 2025 field season.

Read the article [here](#).

PUBLICATION HIGHLIGHTS

This section highlights recent glacial-lake-related publications from our team and from researchers across the wider scientific community.

Khadka, N., Liu, W., Shrestha, M., **Watson, C.S.**, Acharya, S., Chen, X. and Gouli, M.R., 2025. Multidisciplinary Perspectives in Understanding Himalayan glacial lakes in a Climate Challenged World. *Information Geography*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infgeo.2025.100002>

Kumar, R. and Vijay, S., 2026. Automated satellite-based glacial lake inventory and change detection in High Mountain Asia. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-026-35446-0>

Rawlins, L.D., Watson, C.S., Bhambri, R., Khadka, N. and Chand, M.B., 2026. Glacial Lake Observatory (GLO): Annual dataset of glacial lakes in Nepal and transboundary catchments (2017–2024). *Earth System Science Data Discussions*, 2026, pp.1-33. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-751>

Sui, Y., Hu, Z., Zhang, K., Yan, D., Su, Y., Xu, J., Wang, R. and Feng, M., 2025. A comprehensive water bodies dataset of high-mountain Asia. *Scientific Data*, 12(1), p.1350. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-05659-5>

Wang, R., Li, X., Shi, F., Yang, Y., Zheng, H., Liu, J., Liu, L. and Liu, C., 2026. A comprehensive high-resolution lake inventory across the highly heterogeneous Tibetan Plateau from 2020 Sentinel-2 imagery using deep learning. *GIScience & Remote Sensing*, 63(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15481603.2026.2620151>

TEAM SPOTLIGHT

Dr C. Scott Watson

GLO Project PI

Role on the project

“I am a UKRI Future Leaders Fellow leading the Glacial Lake Observatory for Flood Hazards Impacted by Changing Climate (GLO-FHICC) project. I use satellite data, modelling, and field measurements to investigate the evolution of glacial lakes and their impacts on glacier loss, water resources, and natural hazards.”

Project Highlight

“My highlight is having the opportunity to work with such a diverse and dedicated team including researchers, students, project partners, mountain guides, support staff, and media partners.”

Outside of Work

“Often adventuring, running, paddling, climbing, DIY-ing. I also lead adventure training activities, first aid, and health and safety for a local *Royal Air Force Air Cadets* squadron”

Dr Lauren Rawlins

GLO Postdoctoral Research Associate

Role on the project

“I provide remote-sensing and field-based UAV expertise to understand how glacial lakes develop and how flood hazards evolve, helping improve disaster preparedness and water security across High Mountain Asia. My background is in glacial hydrology, remote sensing, and photogrammetry.”

Project Highlight

“My highlight of the project so far was Himalayan fieldwork in 2025 - being surrounded by such spectacular landscapes whilst doing great and important science, meeting local people, and pushing myself to new personal goals (including some serious altitudes). Excited to return this year!”

Outside of Work

“When I’m not staring at glaciers, I’m usually out exploring with my dog, Eska, or getting stuck into something crafty.”

View of Ama Dablam (2025)

KEEP IN TOUCH...

To keep up-to-date with project updates, fieldwork videos, and to contribute to the growing GLO open access data platform, please follow us:

[Glacial-lake-observatory.org](https://glacial-lake-observatory.org)

[@GlacialLakeObservatory](https://www.instagram.com/GlacialLakeObservatory)

[Glacial Lake Observatory](https://www.facebook.com/GlacialLakeObservatory)

[Glacial Lake Observatory](https://zenodo.org/communities/glacial-lake-observatory)

[Glacial Lake Observatory](https://www.youtube.com/GlacialLakeObservatory)